

Appendix S3. Estimating broad-sense heritability.

We estimated broad-sense heritability (H^2) under frequentist and Bayesian frameworks. We calculated H^2 by dividing V_G by model-estimated V_P . For non-Gaussian traits, we were unable to extract phenotypic variance from the frequentist models (*i.e.*, residual variance is non-identifiable in Poisson models). As a work around, we calculated phenotypic variance on the latent scale by adding 1 to all observations, transforming each observation with log, and then calculating the variance.